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Reassessing the Antioch Church as a Model of Ecclesial Health in Acts 11: 19- 30 and 13:1-3

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Abstract

Questions about what truly constitutes church health continue to occupy an important place in contemporary ecclesiology, especially at a time when church growth is often assessed more by programmes and numerical increase than by theological depth. This study examines the church at Antioch in Acts of the Apostles 11:19–30 and 13:1–3 in order to identify the qualities that accounted for its vitality and effectiveness. Using an exegetical and theological reading of Luke's narrative in conversation with relevant ecclesiological and missiological scholarship, the study shows that the Antioch church was marked by the following: genuine conversion, active evangelistic witness, ethnic inclusiveness, Spirit-directed leadership, intentional discipleship, the exercise of spiritual gifts, generous stewardship, and sustained devotion to prayer, worship, fasting, and scriptural instruction. Its responsiveness to the Holy Spirit in mission further underlines its importance in the spread of early Christianity. Accordingly, the article argues that the Antioch church continues to offer valuable theological and practical insight for churches seeking spiritual vitality, missional faithfulness, and transformative community life.

Keywords: Antioch Church, Ecclesiology, Missional Church, Church Health, Discipleship

Introduction

Church health should not be assessed merely by size, structure, or material resources, but by faithfulness to the purposes of God. Rick Warren identifies these purposes as worship, fellowship, discipleship, ministry, and evangelism (Warren, 1995). A church is therefore healthy when it is shaped by purpose rather than sustained only by programmes. In many contexts, however, churches have become weighed down by activities that no longer respond meaningfully to present realities. Some programmes continue largely because of tradition, even when they contribute little to vitality or missional fruitfulness. This situation calls for renewed reflection on the relevance of existing structures, ministries, and activities. At times, renewal may require restructuring, merging, renaming, or discontinuing certain programmes so that the church may serve more effectively in its context and align more closely with the mission of God. Against this background, the question of what constitutes a healthy church becomes especially important. Although there are many contemporary models of church growth, not all are sufficiently rooted in Scripture. There is therefore a need to return to the New Testament for biblically grounded patterns of ecclesial vitality.

This article examines the church at Antioch as a biblical example of a healthy church in order to draw theological insight and practical implications for contemporary Christian communities. It considers the historical and biblical setting of the Antioch church, identifies the features that account for its health and vitality, and reflects on the significance of those features for church life and mission today. These concerns also shape the guiding questions of the study: what characteristics marked the Antioch church as a healthy Christian community, how did it display spiritual vitality and missional engagement, and in what ways can its example inform contemporary ecclesial practice? Methodologically, the study employs an exegetical and theological analysis of Acts of the Apostles 11:19–30 and 13:1–3. Through close engagement with Luke’s narrative and selected ecclesiological and missiological scholarship, the article interprets the Antioch church both as a historical community and as a scripturally grounded model for contemporary reflection.

Scripture presents several churches whose life and witness offer important lessons for later generations. Among them, the church at Antioch stands out as an especially instructive example. For that reason, this study treats Antioch as a model of church health. To describe something as a model is to

regard it as a pattern worthy of serious consideration and, where appropriate, careful imitation. Adeleke (2020) fittingly refers to the Antioch church as a “Gold Church,” emphasising its health, vibrancy, militancy, and fruitfulness. What makes Antioch particularly significant is that it pursued God’s agenda within a morally complex environment. That reality makes the church highly relevant for contemporary reflection. In order to interpret its life and witness within a wider ecclesiological and missiological frame, this article employs the Missional Church paradigm as its primary theoretical lens.

Theoretical Framework

This study is framed by the Missional Church paradigm, which understands the church as a people called and sent by God to participate in the *missio Dei*, that is, God’s redemptive work in the world (Bosch, 1991; Newbigin, 1995). Within this perspective, the church’s identity and practice are shaped less by institutional maintenance than by participation in God’s saving purpose. This makes the paradigm especially appropriate for reading the Antioch narrative in Acts of the Apostles 11:19–30 and 13:1–3. In these texts, the Antioch church appears as a Spirit-directed and mission-shaped community, distinguished by active witness, inclusive fellowship, and attentiveness to the Holy Spirit. Its commissioning of Barnabas and Saul further reveals its character as a sending church. Seen through this lens, the key features of Antioch are best understood as expressions of a community deeply involved in God’s mission and therefore as indicators of ecclesial health and missional vitality. However, while the Missional Church paradigm provides a helpful theological lens, it must be critically grounded in careful exegesis to avoid the risk of reading contemporary missional assumptions back into the biblical text.

Conceptual Clarification

For the purpose of clarity and analytical precision, it is essential to define the key concepts underpinning this study, namely, healthy church, and model, as they are employed within this discourse.

Healthy Church

A healthy church is not simply a church that records numerical increase or displays organisational success; rather, it is a church marked by spiritual

vitality and fidelity to biblical truth. Such a community consists of genuinely converted believers and is marked by sound teaching, meaningful worship, mutual care, deliberate discipleship, and active participation in mission (Eph. 4:11–16; Matt. 28:19–20). Warren (1995) argues that health precedes growth, insisting that when a church is healthy, growth follows naturally. In a similar vein, Schwarz (1996) points to quality characteristics such as empowering leadership, gift-based ministry, and passionate spirituality as signs of church health. Together, these insights show that authentic church health rests on spiritual maturity and effective ministry rather than on outward success alone.

Model

The term “model” may be understood as a pattern, framework, or example that guides reflection, adaptation, or imitation. Within ecclesiological discussion, a model functions as a conceptual and practical aid for understanding the nature and mission of the church. Dulles (2002) argues that models help illuminate the church from different, yet complementary, angles. To describe the Antioch church as a model, therefore, is to suggest that its life and ministry offer a meaningful and instructive pattern for thinking about contemporary church life and mission.

The Context of the Antioch Church

Antioch, the city in which this church emerged, ranked after Rome and Alexandria in prominence in the ancient world. Founded by Seleucus Nicator around 300 B.C. and named after his father Antiochus Epiphanes, it developed into a major centre of political, commercial, and cultural life (MacGregor, 1984). Ogilvie (1983) notes that it was regarded as the “eyes” of Asia within the wider Roman Empire, while Strauss (2008) describes it as a bustling cosmopolitan centre shaped by trade, migration, and constant movement. Greek culture exerted strong influence in the city, and Antioch was known for religious diversity, public entertainment, and moral excess. Its famous sanctuary at Daphne, with its associated cultic immorality, contributed to the city’s notorious reputation (MacGregor, 1984). Kisau (2006) likewise portrays Antioch as one of the morally corrupt cities of the ancient world. It was within this setting that the church at Antioch was born.

The historical and social setting of Antioch can be clarified further by extra-biblical witnesses, especially Flavius Josephus and Strabo. Josephus refers to the spread of Jewish communities throughout the Greco-Roman world and indicates that significant Jewish populations were present in major cities such as Antioch, where they enjoyed notable civic and religious privileges (Josephus, 1987, *Antiquities* 12.119–124; *Wars* 7.43–45). This background sheds light on why the gospel was first proclaimed to Jews in Antioch, as Acts 11:19 indicates. Strabo, for his part, portrays Antioch as one of the major urban centres of the Roman East, notable for its strategic position, economic importance, and cultural diversity (Strabo, 1984, *Geography* 16.2.5). Such an environment facilitated the movement of ideas and the spread of new religious communities, including Christianity. Although neither author describes the inner life of the Christian congregation in Antioch, their testimony helps situate the rise of the church within the realities of Jewish diaspora life and Greco-Roman urban culture. This background, in turn, strengthens the theological reading of Antioch as an inclusive and mission-oriented community in Luke’s narrative.

Yet, for all its moral and cultural complexity, Antioch was penetrated by the power of the gospel, and many Gentiles came to faith in Christ. In keeping with Romans 1:16, the gospel proved itself to be the power of God for salvation to all who believe. Antioch thus became the location of the earliest major Gentile church mentioned in Acts (Acts 11:19–30). It also became a strategic centre of Gentile Christianity, the place where believers were first called Christians (Acts 11:26), and the church from which the first major missionary sending took place (Acts 13:1–3). In that sense, Antioch became one of the launch points for the wider missionary advance of early Christianity. If the grace of God could establish a vibrant church in a city as morally troubled as Antioch, then there is good reason to believe that God can still raise healthy churches in difficult contexts today, including Nigeria and beyond.

Features of Antioch Church

A careful study of Acts 11:19–30 and 13:1–3 reveals several defining features that characterised the church at Antioch as a healthy and mission-oriented community. These features provide a compelling biblical model from which the contemporary church can draw theological insight and practical application. The church at Antioch demonstrates that ecclesial health is not

accidental but is rooted in spiritual vitality, doctrinal soundness, and intentional mission engagement.

1. The Antioch Church Was Composed of Regenerated Believers Who Had Responded to the Gospel of Christ (Acts 11:19-21)

Acts 11:19 resumes the movement of the narrative already introduced in Acts 8:4. The expression “those who were scattered” points to believers dispersed by the persecution that followed Stephen’s martyrdom. Luke had earlier noted that these scattered believers “went about preaching the word” (Acts 8:4), turning suffering into an avenue for gospel expansion. In Acts 11 the story continues as these believers reach Phoenicia, Cyprus, and Antioch with the message of Christ. Bruce (1988) rightly observes that persecution, though painful, became one of the means through which the gospel moved beyond Jerusalem. Christianity in Jerusalem was therefore not extinguished by persecution; it was dispersed and extended.

The text indicates that those who constituted the church in Antioch were individuals who had personally encountered the message of Christ and responded in faith. Acts 11:21 affirms that “the hand of the Lord was with them, and a great number of people believed and turned to the Lord.” This indicates that the Antioch church emerged through genuine conversion rather than social affiliation or institutional expansion. Bock (2007) observes that the phrase “believed and turned to the Lord” highlights the transformative nature of the gospel response, indicating both faith and repentance as essential elements in the formation of the early Christian community. This narrative provides an important theological principle for church planting and ecclesial health.

While various missionary strategies, such as house-to-house evangelism, medical outreach, and community development initiatives, may be employed in church planting, these methods must be accompanied by the clear proclamation of the gospel of Jesus Christ. The Antioch model suggests that a healthy church is fundamentally composed of regenerated believers who have personally responded to the message of Christ and whose lives demonstrate the transforming power of the gospel. In this sense, the vitality of the church is rooted not merely in organisational structures or numerical growth but in the authentic conversion and spiritual commitment of its members. Just as a sound foundation is essential for the stability and

longevity of any structure of value, so also the membership base of a church is fundamental to its overall health.

2. The Antioch Church Was Characterised by Believers Who Actively Witnessed for Christ (Acts 11:20)

Following Stephen's martyrdom, many believers were forced out of Jerusalem and spread into places such as Phoenicia, Cyprus, and Antioch. Luke notes in Acts 11:19 that, even in dispersion, they continued to speak about Christ wherever they went. At first, their witness focused mainly on Jews, reflecting the early movement's Jewish setting. Soon, however, some believers in Antioch began to announce the good news about the Lord Jesus to Gentiles as well (Acts 11:20). Stott (1990) sees in this development a major advance in the missionary expansion of the early church and a concrete expression of the universal reach of the gospel. Rather than silencing the believers, persecution became a catalyst for gospel expansion. Their perseverance also echoes the conviction of Romans 8:35–38 that nothing can separate God's people from His love in Christ. In that way, the early church embodied the missionary thrust later expressed in Matthew 28:19–20.

A similar pattern can be observed in contemporary Christian communities that face persecution yet remain steadfast in their faith. Testimonies shared by some believers from northern Nigeria during the 2025 Nigerian Baptist Convention Annual Session illustrate this resilience. These Christians narrated how, despite attacks on their communities, displacement from their homes, and persistent threats from extremist groups, they have continued to gather for worship, nurture new believers, and proclaim the gospel within their communities. Some recounted how some church buildings that were destroyed were later rebuilt, while others testified that the suffering they endured strengthened their commitment to Christ and deepened their resolve to evangelise. Such testimonies demonstrate that persecution has not extinguished their faith but has instead intensified their dedication to Christ's mission.

Like the believers in the early church, these contemporary witnesses embody a living testimony that faith in Christ cannot be suppressed by suffering, and that the proclamation of the gospel continues even in the midst of adversity. A healthy church is characterised by a deep commitment to evangelism, where both pastors and members demonstrate a genuine passion for soul-winning. Such a church is fundamentally a witnessing

church in which every member participates in the proclamation of the gospel (Bosch, 2011; Stott, 1990).

3. The Antioch Church Demonstrated Inclusiveness in Mission and Multicultural Fellowship (Acts 11:20; 13:1)

Although the Antioch believers were active witnesses for Christ, their mission did not remain confined to one ethnic or cultural constituency. On the contrary, the Antioch story shows that faithful gospel witness moves outward in an inclusive manner toward people of differing backgrounds. Luke narrates this development with care. At first, the scattered believers spoke primarily to Jews (Acts 11:19b), but Acts 11:20 records a decisive broadening of scope when some from Cyprus and Cyrene began speaking also to Greeks, proclaiming the good news about the Lord Jesus. Keener (2012) understands this move as a significant stage in the church's missionary expansion beyond the Jewish community. The leadership profile in Acts 13:1 reinforces the same point: Barnabas, Simeon called Niger, Lucius of Cyrene, Manaen, and Saul represent a notably diverse group in ethnicity and social location. Antioch was therefore not defined by racial, ethnic, class, or cultural exclusion. Its life together displays another important mark of a healthy church, mission joined with multicultural fellowship.

Inclusiveness is the willingness to embrace people of different backgrounds and to treat them with fairness and dignity within the community of faith. A healthy church, therefore, does not restrict its ministry to a particular category of people but intentionally reaches out to all. The theological basis for such inclusiveness lies in the universal scope of God's love. John 3:16 underscores the universal scope of God's love, "for God so loved the world", highlighting that divine love is not restricted to a particular people but is extended to all humanity, even though its saving benefits are appropriated through faith (Carson, 1991; Köstenberger, 2004). The term "world" (*kosmos*) in this context points to humanity in its fallen condition, thereby emphasising both the breadth of God's love and the gracious initiative of God toward all people (Morris, 1995). A healthy church therefore resists every form of discrimination and demonstrates openness to people of different languages, cultures, and social contexts. Furthermore, the Great Commission commands believers to "make disciples of all nations" (Matt. 28:19), emphasising that the mission of the church is universal rather than

limited to a particular group or nation. Whenever the church becomes sectionalised or tribalised in its outlook, it departs from the biblical model of church health.

4. The Antioch Church Demonstrated Evident Divine Approval in Its Mission (11:21)

The inclusive reach of the Antioch mission was accompanied by clear signs of divine approval. What happened there was not merely the product of human zeal or careful planning; it bore the marks of God's own presence and favour. Luke captures this in Acts 11:21 by saying that "the Lord's hand was with them." In biblical usage, such language points to God's active empowerment of human action for the accomplishment of His purposes. Here it signals that the believers' ministry in Antioch stood in harmony with the will of God. The result makes this plain: many believed and turned to the Lord (Acts 11:21). Bock (2007) therefore rightly interprets the growth of the Antioch church not as a merely human achievement but as evidence of God's sovereign work in advancing the gospel.

This observation highlights an important characteristic of a healthy church. When a church operates in alignment with God's mission and faithfully proclaims the gospel, it experiences the empowering presence of God in its ministry. Keener (2012) similarly observes that the success of the mission in Antioch reflects divine endorsement of the believers' outreach, particularly in their willingness to extend the gospel beyond traditional ethnic boundaries. The growth of the Antioch church therefore illustrates how God's approval accompanies ministries that are rooted in obedience to His redemptive purpose. Conversely, churches that pursue activities disconnected from God's mission risk losing their spiritual vitality. When churches merely imitate the programmes or strategies of others without discerning God's direction, they may appear active yet remain spiritually ineffective. The narrative of Antioch reminds contemporary churches that genuine fruitfulness does not arise from competition, imitation, or human ingenuity alone, but from faithful participation in what God Himself is doing. Ministry that aligns with God's will produces results that endure because it is sustained by divine power rather than human ambition. The divine affirmation evident in Antioch further strengthens the argument that the Antioch church stands as a compelling biblical model of a healthy

church, one whose ministry is sustained by God's presence and whose growth reflects the outworking of His redemptive purpose.

5. The Antioch Church Manifested the Evident Grace of God through Its Life and Ministry (11:23)

After noting that "the Lord's hand was with them" (Acts 11:21), Luke goes on to recount the visit of Barnabas, who had been sent from Jerusalem to assess what was happening in Antioch. According to Acts 11:23, Barnabas arrived, saw the grace of God at work, rejoiced, and urged the believers to remain faithful to the Lord with resolute hearts. His response indicates that the church's growth in Antioch involved more than increasing numbers; it also involved visible evidence of God's transforming grace in the community. The phrase "the grace of God" here points to God's saving activity among the Gentile believers. For many Jewish Christians this development was theologically significant, since covenant privilege had long been associated with Israel. Yet Antioch demonstrated that God's grace was being extended to all who believed. Keener (2012) notes that Barnabas recognised this development as evidence that the gospel's expansion beyond Jewish boundaries belonged to God's redemptive purpose. Stott (1990) similarly observes that Barnabas' joy sprang from his ability to discern the genuine work of God in the lives of these believers. Antioch therefore illustrates that a healthy church is marked not only by outward growth, but by the palpable evidence of divine grace in its common life.

6. The Antioch Church Was Led by Spirit-Filled, Mission-Oriented, and Encouraging Leaders (11:23-24)

Closely connected with this visible evidence of grace was the quality of leadership that nurtured the Antioch church. Once Barnabas discerned God's work among the Gentile believers (Acts 11:23), Luke also draws attention to the kind of leader he was. Barnabas rejoiced over what God was doing and encouraged the believers to remain true to the Lord with wholehearted devotion. This was in keeping with the character already associated with him in Jerusalem, where his very name had become linked with encouragement (Acts 4:36–37). Acts 11:24 describes him as a good man, full of the Holy Spirit and of faith. Keener (2012) notes that such spiritual discernment enabled Barnabas to recognise authentic faith among the Gentiles and to nurture unity in the growing church. Stott (1990) also

regards him as an ideal envoy because he could recognise and affirm the work of God in others while strengthening them in faith.

From the testimony about Barnabas, one can see that healthy churches are nurtured by leaders who are liberal-minded, generous-hearted, sympathetic, full of faith, celebrate the spiritual growth of others, encourage believers in their faith, and remain passionate about evangelism and church planting. Such leaders do not feel threatened by the success of other ministries but instead rejoice when the gospel advances and lives are transformed. This insight is particularly relevant for contemporary Christian communities. Churches and denominational structures must be intentional in selecting leaders who possess spiritual maturity, missional passion, and the capacity to encourage others. When individuals who are filled with the Holy Spirit and committed to the mission of God are entrusted with leadership responsibilities, the church is better positioned to grow spiritually and expand its witness.

7. The Antioch Church Demonstrated Intentional Commitment to the Spiritual Formation and Discipleship of Believers through Sustained Teaching Ministry (11:25-26)

Having seen God's grace at work among the new believers (Acts 11:23–24), Barnabas also recognised that the growing congregation needed sustained teaching and discipleship if it was to develop in depth and stability. He understood that one effective way of raising agents of kingdom transformation is by making disciples who in turn make other disciples, thereby extending the chain of discipleship. For that reason, he brought Saul into the work. Antioch's cosmopolitan environment, with its political complexity, religious plurality, and moral pressures, made such instruction especially necessary. New believers in that setting needed doctrinal formation and pastoral guidance if they were to mature in Christ. Barnabas therefore travelled to Tarsus to look for Paul and brought him back to Antioch to share in the ministry of teaching (Acts 11:25–26). His action shows both discernment and humility.

Barnabas knew that he needed help if he was to make the most of the opportunities that the city of Antioch presented to the church. Rather than attempting to manage the growing church alone, he recognised the importance of collaborative ministry (Akerle, 2025). In doing so, he also helped to open the door for Saul's future ministry among the Gentiles,

fulfilling the divine commission earlier declared concerning him: “This man is my chosen instrument to proclaim my name to the Gentiles” (Acts 9:15). The partnership between Barnabas and Saul illustrates the value of complementary leadership in the life of the church. As Oderinde, Akerele, and Obasola (2019) opine, the work of building a healthy church requires cooperation rather than competition among Christian leaders.

Acts 11:26 further records that Barnabas and Saul spent an entire year teaching the believers in Antioch. Their sustained commitment to instruction and discipleship produced visible results within the community. The believers not only professed faith in Christ but increasingly reflected His character in their daily lives. Consequently, the disciples were “first called Christians in Antioch” (Acts 11:26). The designation “Christian” was not originally a title adopted by the church itself; rather, it was a name given by the people of the city who recognised that the believers belonged to Christ and reflected His life in their conduct. The suffix *-ian* (Greek: *-ianos*) conveys the idea of belonging to or identifying with a particular person, often indicating allegiance or association. In the New Testament context, the term “Christian” (*Christianos*) thus signifies those who belong to or are identified with Christ (Acts 11:26) (Bruce, 1988; Keener, 2012). In early Christianity, therefore, the term “Christian” functioned not only as a label of social identification but also as a marker of spiritual formation, reflecting a community whose beliefs, values, and practices were patterned after the life and teachings of Jesus.

The transformation of the Antioch believers highlights the central role of discipleship in the early church. In the New Testament, the term “disciple” is frequently used to describe followers of Jesus, while the word “Christian” appears only three times (Acts 11:26; 26:28; 1 Pet. 4:16). This linguistic pattern underscores the early church’s emphasis on discipleship as the process through which believers were formed into faithful followers of Christ. Discipleship involved not merely intellectual instruction but the shaping of a new way of life characterised by obedience to Christ. As Paul later affirmed, those who belong to Christ become “a new creation” in whom “old things have passed away” and “all things have become new” (2 Cor. 5:17). The experience of the Antioch church therefore provides an important lesson for contemporary Christian communities. Churches that desire spiritual vitality must intentionally prioritise discipleship as a central dimension of their ministry. By investing deeply in discipleship, the leaders

in Antioch cultivated a community whose identity and conduct reflected Christ Himself. In this way, the church in Antioch further confirms its significance as a biblical model of a healthy church.

8. The Antioch Church Fostered the Exercise of Spiritual Gifts for the Edification and Growth of the Church (Acts 11:27,28; 13:1-2)

Closely related to Antioch's emphasis on discipleship and spiritual formation was the active place of spiritual gifts in the life of the church. A healthy church intentionally creates room for believers to discover, develop, and deploy their gifts for the building up of the body of Christ (Omomola, 2017). Believers bring natural abilities, spiritual endowments, and acquired skills, all of which may be harnessed for the strengthening of the local church. As disciples mature through teaching and formation, they are also encouraged to take part in the church's life and mission by using these God-given capacities. Such participation helps the church function as a living body in which every member has a meaningful part to play. This was clearly the case in Antioch and forms another reason the church may be regarded as a model of health.

Acts 11:27–28 records that prophets came from Jerusalem to Antioch, and one of them, Agabus, under the influence of the Holy Spirit, foretold that a severe famine would affect the entire Roman world. The presence of prophetic ministry within the Antioch church indicates that the congregation provided an atmosphere in which believers could exercise their spiritual gifts for the benefit of the community. Similarly, Acts 13:1–2 reveals that the church included prophets and teachers among its leaders, demonstrating that different forms of ministry were actively recognised and practised within the congregation. These references suggest that the Antioch church valued the diverse gifts that God had bestowed upon His people. The New Testament consistently emphasises the importance of spiritual gifts in the life of the church. The Apostle Paul identifies a variety of gifts—including apostleship, prophecy, evangelism, pastoral leadership, teaching, service, exhortation, generosity, leadership, mercy, wisdom, knowledge, faith, healing, miracles, discernment, tongues, and interpretation of tongues (Eph. 4:7–13; Rom. 12:6–8; 1 Cor. 12:7–11). These gifts are given by the Holy Spirit not for personal recognition but for the strengthening and unity of the church. As Paul explains, the purpose of

these gifts is “to equip the saints for the work of ministry, for building up the body of Christ” (Eph. 4:12–13).

The experience of the Antioch church therefore illustrates another important feature of a healthy church: believers are encouraged to discover and utilise their gifts in service to God and the Christian community. A church that intentionally creates opportunities for members to serve according to their gifts fosters spiritual growth, mutual edification, and a deeper sense of participation in God’s mission. Leaders play a crucial role in this process by helping members identify their gifts, develop their capacities, and deploy them effectively within the ministry of the church. This principle is particularly significant for contemporary Christian communities. Churches that desire vitality and sustainability must intentionally cultivate an environment where believers, young and old alike, are empowered to use their God-given abilities. When members are encouraged to serve through their natural talents, acquired skills, and spiritual gifts, the entire body of Christ is strengthened and unified in its mission.

9. The Antioch Church Demonstrated Generosity and Sacrificial Giving as an Expression of Christian Solidarity (11:29-30)

As believers in Antioch served through their gifts and ministries, they also expressed their faith through sacrificial generosity. Acts 11:29–30 reports that the disciples, each according to ability, resolved to send relief to the brothers and sisters in Judea, and they did so through Barnabas and Saul. Their response came after Agabus had announced an impending famine (Acts 11:27–28). Rather than waiting to be compelled, the Antioch believers freely chose to support fellow Christians who would likely be affected by the crisis. In doing so, they displayed practical love, spiritual maturity, and solidarity with the wider body of Christ.

Several important features of Christian stewardship are evident in this narrative. First, the giving was voluntary; the believers were not compelled but responded willingly to the needs of others. Second, their giving was proportional, as each person contributed “according to his ability.” Third, their generosity was directed toward meeting the practical needs of fellow believers. These characteristics reflect the broader New Testament teaching on Christian generosity. The Apostle Paul later emphasised that believers should give willingly and cheerfully, not under compulsion, because “God

loves a cheerful giver” (2 Cor. 9:7). Similarly, the early Christian tradition affirmed that “it is more blessed to give than to receive” (Acts 20:35). The generosity of the Antioch believers reveals another important dimension of a healthy church: a community that expresses its faith through tangible acts of compassion and solidarity. When believers give willingly and sacrificially, they demonstrate that their faith extends beyond words to practical expressions of love and service. Such generosity also strengthens the unity of the wider Christian community, as churches support one another in times of need. This principle remains highly relevant for contemporary churches. Healthy congregations cultivate a culture of faithful stewardship in which members contribute their resources to advance the mission of the church and to care for those in need within and outside the local church. As Rainer (2013) observes, committed church members recognise their responsibility to support the ministry of the church through faithful giving and service. When believers embrace this spirit of generosity, the church is better positioned to fulfil its mission and maintain its spiritual vitality. This is exemplified by church in Antioch. Its members demonstrated not only spiritual devotion and active service but also generous and sacrificial giving that strengthened the fellowship of believers and advanced the mission of God.

10. The Antioch Church Demonstrated Sustained Commitment to Spiritual Disciplines (11:26; 13:2-3)

The generosity displayed by the Antioch believers was not merely a humanitarian impulse; it arose from a community whose life was deeply rooted in devotion to God. Their giving formed part of a larger pattern of spiritual formation sustained through disciplined practices. Akerele (2012) notes that believers grow in their relationship with Christ when they intentionally cultivate habits that nourish Christian spirituality. Foster (1998) similarly describes spiritual disciplines as practices through which believers are formed in maturity and responsiveness to God. He groups them broadly into inward, outward, and corporate disciplines. Inward disciplines include meditation, prayer, fasting, and Bible study; outward disciplines include simplicity, solitude, submission, and service; corporate disciplines include confession, worship, guidance, and celebration. Together, these practices strengthen both personal devotion and the shared spiritual life of the church.

The believers in the Antioch church clearly demonstrated their commitment to such disciplines. Acts 11:26 and 13:2–3 indicate that they regularly engaged in teaching, worship, prayer, and fasting while seeking God’s direction. These practices created an atmosphere of spiritual sensitivity in which the Holy Spirit could guide the church’s mission. Jesus Himself emphasised the importance of persistent prayer (Luke 18:1), and the New Testament affirms that “the prayer of a righteous person is powerful and effective” (James 5:16). Within the Antioch community, public worship and prayer were not isolated rituals but expressions of a deeper personal devotion to God. Fasting also played a significant role in the spiritual life of the Antioch believers. Throughout Scripture, fasting is often associated with seeking God’s guidance, deepening spiritual focus, and expressing dependence upon Him. While the Bible does not prescribe a fixed duration for fasting, the practice is consistently presented as a means through which believers draw closer to God and align themselves with His purposes. Equally important was the central role of Scripture in the life of the church. Healthy churches are characterised by a deep commitment to the study and faithful interpretation of God’s Word. The Bible is the inspired Word of God and the final authority for faith and practice (2 Timothy 3:16). The experience of the Antioch church demonstrates that preaching and teaching grounded in Scripture have a transformative impact on the life of the church. John MacArthur (1991) observes that when the Word of God is faithfully taught and applied, it shapes the spiritual character of believers and strengthens the vitality of the church. Churches that prioritise biblical teaching and spiritual formation therefore create environments in which believers can grow in maturity and faithfulness.

In addition, the Antioch church demonstrated the importance of worship as a central element of Christian spirituality. Worship, whether personal or corporate, centres on acknowledging the worth of God and responding to His revealed presence. Genuine worship not only celebrates God but also leads believers toward deeper commitment to His purposes. The experience of Isaiah illustrates this transformative dimension of worship, as his encounter with God resulted in his willingness to respond, “Here am I; send me” (Isa. 6:8). Similarly, in the Antioch church, it was during a time of worship and fasting that the Holy Spirit directed the church to set apart Barnabas and Saul for missionary service (Acts 13:2). The Antioch church shows that a healthy church is characterised by believers who are deeply

devoted to spiritual disciplines that nurture their relationship with God and guide their participation in His mission. Through the study of the Scripture, prayer, fasting, and worship, the believers in Antioch cultivated a spiritually vibrant community that remained attentive to the voice and direction of the Holy Spirit. In this way, the Antioch church once again confirms its significance as a compelling biblical model of a healthy church.

11. The Antioch Church Was Characterised by Obedience to the Holy Spirit and Active Engagement in Mission (13:2-3)

In Antioch, mission was not handled as an abstract subject for endless discussion; it was received as a divine charge to be discerned and obeyed. As the believers worshipped, fasted, and prayed, they responded to the Holy Spirit's direction by setting apart Barnabas and Saul for missionary service (Acts 13:2-3). This portrays a church that was spiritually alert and ready to act. The community understood its calling in the light of Matthew 28:19-20 and embraced the Great Commission as part of its identity. The significance of Antioch for the contemporary church, therefore, lies not in any claim that it was superior to later churches, but in the way Scripture presents it as a biblically grounded example of Spirit-led obedience in mission.

In a healthy church, both leaders and members demonstrate a deep commitment to mission, not with reluctance but with willingness and enthusiasm. Evangelism and church planting are not perceived as burdensome obligations, nor is financial investment in missions viewed as excessive. Rather, members are eager to pray, to give, and to go in obedience to God's call. The example of the Antioch church thus underscores that authentic church health is evidenced by a Spirit-led passion for mission and a readiness to act in obedience to divine instruction.

Conclusion

The Antioch church occupies an important place in Acts as one of the earliest and most influential Christian communities outside Jerusalem. The preceding discussion has shown that it may rightly be viewed as a compelling biblical paradigm of church health. Its vitality is seen in a body of believers marked by genuine conversion, active witness to Christ, inclusiveness across ethnic and cultural lines, and clear evidence of God's grace and approval. It was sustained by Spirit-led, mission-minded leadership, by deliberate discipleship, and by a participatory community life

in which spiritual gifts were exercised, generosity was practised, and prayer, worship, fasting, and scriptural instruction were taken seriously. These interwoven features suggest that Antioch's health arose from responsiveness to the Holy Spirit and active participation in God's redemptive mission. For that reason, the church at Antioch offers a biblically grounded and theologically informed pattern from which contemporary Christian communities may draw insight as they seek spiritual vitality, missional faithfulness, and transformative communal life.

Recommendations for the Contemporary Church

Drawing from the example of the church in Antioch, several practical lessons emerge for contemporary Christian communities that desire to remain spiritually vibrant and missionally effective.

1. ***Prioritise genuine conversion and spiritual transformation:*** Churches should intentionally emphasise the message of the gospel so that membership is grounded in genuine faith in Christ rather than mere religious affiliation. A healthy church begins with people whose lives have been transformed by an authentic encounter with Christ.
2. ***Cultivate a strong culture of discipleship:*** Like Barnabas and Saul who invested time in teaching and nurturing believers, contemporary churches must give serious attention to discipleship. Teaching the Word of God, mentoring believers, and guiding them toward spiritual maturity should remain central to church ministry.
3. ***Promote inclusiveness in mission and fellowship:*** The Antioch church demonstrated that the gospel is for all people. Churches today should intentionally welcome people from diverse cultural, social, and ethnic backgrounds and engage in mission that reaches beyond traditional boundaries.
4. ***Encourage members to discover and use their spiritual gifts:*** Healthy churches create opportunities for members to serve according to the gifts God has given them. Pastors and church leaders should help believers identify, develop, and utilise their gifts for the edification of the church and the advancement of God's mission.
5. ***Strengthen commitment to prayer, spiritual disciplines, and mission:*** The Antioch church was devoted to worship, prayer, fasting, and obedience to the leading of the Holy Spirit. Contemporary churches should likewise cultivate a culture of spiritual devotion that leads to

active participation in evangelism, church planting, and the fulfilment of the Great Commission.

Taken together, these recommendations remind contemporary churches that spiritual vitality and missional effectiveness are sustained when believers remain rooted in Christ, committed to discipleship, and actively engaged in God's redemptive mission in the world.

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